

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Husband's support on the incidence of baby blues in mothers: A literature review study

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Abstract

The puerperium is a period of recovery starting from the completion of labor until the gynecological apparatus returns to its pre-pregnancy state. The duration of the postpartum period lasts for 6-8 weeks. The incidence of postpartum blues in Indonesia (2016) according to USAID (United States Agency for International) is 31 births per 1000 Indonesian population. The aim is to determine the husband's support for the incidence of baby blues in mothers. The method in this study uses a literature review, with the number of articles being 5 articles using the same keywords. The results of the literature review of the five journals found that husband support affects the incidence of baby blues in mothers. In conclusion, based on the analysis that has been done, it is concluded that mothers who are in the postpartum period and lack good support from their husbands will experience baby blues on average. One of the risk factors that can influence the incidence of baby blues is husband support. Husband's support has a big or significant influence on the incidence of baby blues experienced by postpartum mothers.

Keywords: The puerperium; Postpartum; Baby Blues; Husband Support; Mother.

1. Introduction

A baby born to a mother can make a big change in the mother's life, both in terms of the mother's habits, the mother's relationship with her husband and other family. According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2016, the number of women giving birth continues to increase every year to 90.88%, there are 289,000 women die during and after pregnancy and childbirth.

The puerperium is a period of recovery, starting from the completion of labor until the gynecological apparatus returns to its pre-pregnancy state. The puerperium duration lasts for 6-8 weeks [9]. Postpartum is included in the transition phase which causes some mothers to experience a life crisis. Some mothers can experience psychological changes including increased anxiety, continuous sadness, feelings of wanting to hurt themselves to hurt the baby, and inability to breastfeed. Mothers who are unable to adjust to psychological changes will experience significant stress and can continue to develop baby blues.

Data according to WHO (2018) notes that the prevalence of postpartum blues in general within the scope of the world population is 3-8% with 50% of cases occurring in mothers with productive age, namely 20-50 years [11]. The incidence of postpartum blues in Indonesia according to USAID (United States Agency for International) in 2016 was 31 births per 1000 Indonesian population. Indonesia is ranked the highest in ASEAN, which is in fourth place after Laos, which has 26 births per 1000 population [11].

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Several factors can cause postpartum blues, one of which is husband support. Husband support has a very important relationship during the onset of postpartum blues because mothers can feel safe and comfortable when support is provided during labor until the postpartum period by their husbands [2]. If the husband does not provide support or just leaves it alone, the mother can experience sadness, overwhelm, and emotional instability that is felt.

Many factors that cause baby blues, one of which is husband support, make researchers want to examine further by conducting a deeper review through a literature review.

The purpose of the literature review is to identify the literature regarding husband support for the incidence of baby blues in mothers.

2. Methods

This type of research is a literature review. A literature review is an overview of the literature at a certain time related to a particular topic [7]. The design used in this research is a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) with the type of research being Library research. The process of collecting references and research journals uses secondary data obtained from research results that have been conducted by previous researchers. Secondary data sources are journals with the same topic.

The databases and search engines used are Google Scholar and Science Direct. Researchers found 5 journals that match the criteria of the researcher's topic.

3. Results and discussion

From the 5 journals, it was found that the average results of the journal researchers said that husband support affects the incidence of baby blues in mothers. The results of the literature review can be seen in the table below.

Based on the results of the study, it was obtained that mothers who do not get enough support from their husbands had more experience with baby blues. This is consistent with research conducted by Rahayu, Sunanto, and Ekasari (2023)[4] and Siringo-ringo (2022)[6] where most husbands did not support postpartum mothers who were experiencing postpartum blues. Emotional support obtained from husbands is needed by mothers during the postpartum period. Husband support can be realized in the form of care and psychological relationships between husbands and wives.

The husband is the family member who has the closest relationship with the mother. Any action taken by the husband can have an impact on the mother's psychological state. Mothers require the support of their husbands during their postpartum period. If she does not receive support from her husband, she may experience fatigue when taking care of the baby, which in turn can make her experience baby blues [6].

Factors that can influence the occurrence of postpartum blues have signs and symptoms that are the result of a multi-factorial mechanism. These factors are hormonal factors, physical activity factors that can cause fatigue due to activities of caring for the baby, breastfeeding, changing diapers, and psychosocial factors which include age, education, occupation, husband support, and pregnancy status. Of these factors, there is a cause of the highest incidence of postpartum blues, namely the lack of husband's support for mothers from pregnancy to postpartum [3].

Research by Eka, Yuni, & Asep (2023)[8] describes that the causes of baby blues syndrome are changes in hormones, stress, breast milk not coming out, frustration, and lack of support provided by husbands. Postpartum women need attention and support from the family, especially the closest family, namely the husband to help take care of the baby or just provide support emotional, informational, instrumental, and appraisal support. The results showed that the husband's support in the good category was 25 (80.6%) respondents, while the husband's support in the moderate category was 6 (19.4%) respondents. So it can be concluded that mothers do not experience postpartum blues because of good husband support. These results are consistent with research by Anggraini (2017)[1], where the husband's role is the first person to provide encouragement and support to the wife. The husband is also an important figure who realizes that there are differences in his wife. Mothers who get support from their husbands can feel loved and cared for so that mothers will feel more prepared to take care of their babies and avoid the baby blues.

Husband support can be provided through emotional support to the mother. Emotional support can be in the form of taking the time to play with the baby to encourage the mother if the mother feels exhausted with daily work. Positive support from the husband can have a positive impact on the mother's condition during the postpartum period. This is

in line with research conducted by Samria (2021)[5], regarding the relationship between husband support and the incidence of postpartum blues in urban areas. Where the results of the analysis showed that there were 19 respondents (47.5%) who suffered from postpartum blues and did not get husband support. Meanwhile, 11 respondents (27.5%) did not suffer from postpartum blues and received good support from their husbands.

Table 1 List of articles

No	Title of journal	Research ers	Source	Result
1	The relationship between husband's support and the occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum mothers	Septi F., Sunanto, & Tutik Ekasari	Jurnal Ilmiah Kesehatan Rustida Vol. 10, No. 02 Juli 2023. p-ISSN 2356-2528; e-ISSN 2620-9640	Based on the results of cross-tabulation between husband support and the incidence of postpartum blues in postpartum women, it shows that most of the postpartum women who experience postpartum blues do not get husband support as many as 17 people (53.2%). So based on the results of the chi-square test with a p-value of 0.000 which shows a significant value, meaning that H0 is rejected. It means that there is a relationship between husband support and the occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum women in the Tempursari Health Center work area in 2022.
2	Characteristics of postpartum mothers and husband support with baby blues syndrome	Ni Wayan Eka W., Ni Komang Yuni R., & Asep A.	Jurnal Ilmiah Kebidanan Vol. 11, No. 01. DOI: https://doi.org/10.33992/jik.v11i1.2440	Based on the distribution table of the characteristics of postpartum mothers, most of them are 20-35 years old as many as 25 respondents (80.6%). Based on the distribution of husband's support for postpartum mothers, most of them were found to be in the good category, totaling 25 respondents (80.6%). And based on the distribution of postpartum mothers with baby blues there were 6 people (19.4%) who experienced baby blues syndrome.
3	The relationship between husband support and the incidence of postpartum blues in primiparous mothers in the Sigompul Health Center work area, Lintong Nihuta District, Humbangsaud utan Regency	Esther Siringo-ringo	Jurnal Riset Rumpun Ilmu Kesehatan (JURRIKES) Vol. 01, No. 02. e-ISSN: 2828-9374; p-ISSN: 2828-9366, Hal 306-319	Based on the characteristics table, most of the respondents were in the age group of 20-35 years (55%). Based on the distribution of the incidence of postpartum blues, it is known that 42 out of 80 respondents had postpartum blues (52.5%). Based on the distribution of husband support, 45 respondents didn't get husband support (56.3%). After doing the chi-square test, the p-value is 0.004, meaning that there is a relationship between the husband's support and the incidence of postpartum blues.
4	The relationship between husband's support and the incidence of postpartum blues in urban areas	Samria & Indah Haerunnisa	J-kemas vol 07 no 1 mei 2021 hal 52-58. e-ISSN: 2541-4542. DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.35329/jkemas.v7i1	The results of analyzing the relationship between the two variables above using the chi-square statistical test obtained significance, $p=0.000$, $p=0.003 < \alpha 0.05$. So there is a relationship between husband support and the incidence of postpartum blues in urban areas. Of the 40 respondents, 6 respondents (15%) suffered from postpartum blues and received husband support, and 19 respondents (47.5%) suffered from postpartum blues and did not receive husband support. While as many as 11 respondents (27.5%) did not suffer from postpartum blues and received husband support and as many as 4 respondents (10%) did

				not suffer from postpartum blues and did not get husband support.
5	The relationship between husband support and postpartum blues in pregnant women	Yuanita W. & Fathiya L.	https://repository.um-surabaya.ac.id/5903/1/1/Laporan Penelitian Bu Yuanita Wulandari - Done.pdf	Based on the table of characteristics of respondents regarding husband support, it shows that most respondents have good husband support 55 respondents (73.3%) and a small proportion of respondents have less husband support (5%). Based on the table of characteristics of respondents based on the occurrence of postpartum blues, most respondents did not experience postpartum blues as many as 57 respondents (76%) and a small proportion experienced postpartum blues as many as 18 respondents (24%). Based on the cross-tabulation between husband support and the occurrence of postpartum blues, most respondents had good husband support with no postpartum blues.

4. Conclusion

Mothers who are in the postpartum period and do not get good support from their husbands on average will experience baby blues. One of the risk factors that can affect the incidence of baby blues is husband support. Husband's support has a big or significant influence on the incidence of baby blues experienced by postpartum mothers.

Compliance with ethical standards

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References

- [1] Anggaraini, H. (2017). The Relationship Between Husband Support, Parity, and KP-IBU Participation with the Incidence of Baby Blues in Postpartum Mothers in the Pajang Health Center Working Area, Surakarta City.
- [2] Kurniawati, N., Isa, L. M. (2021). The Effect of Husband Support on the Incidence of Baby Blues. 1(4), P. 529.
- [3] Nirwana Ade B. (2011). Maternal Infant and Child Psychology. Yogyakarta: Nuha Medika. EGC Medical Book Publisher.
- [4] Rahayu, S.F., Sunanto, S. and Ekasari, T. (2023). Relationship between husband support and the occurrence of postpartum blues in postpartum mothers. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kesehatan Rustida*, 10(2). pp. 87–95. doi:10.55500/jikr.v10i2.192.
- [5] Samria, S. and Indah Haerunnisa, I.H. (2021). The relationship between husband support and the incidence of postpartum blues in urban areas. *J-KESMAS: Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat*. 7(1), p. 52. doi:10.35329/jkesmas.v7i1.1952.
- [6] Siringo-ringo, E. (2022). The Relationship of Husband Support to the Incidence of Postpartum Blues in Primiparous Mothers in the Sigompul Health Center Working Area, Lintong Nihuta District, Humbanghasundutan Regency. *Jurnal Riset Rumpun Ilmu Kesehatan (JURRIKES)*. 1(2). Pp 306-319.
- [7] Suryani dan Hendryadi. 2016. Quantitative Research Methods: Theory and Application to Research in Management and Islamic Economics. Jakarta: Kencana.
- [8] Wahyuni, N.W., Yuni Rahyani, N.K. and Senjaya, A.A. (2023). Characteristics of postpartum mothers with baby blues syndrome. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kebidanan (The Journal Of Midwifery)*, 11(1), pp. 114–120. doi:10.33992/jik.v11i1.2440.
- [9] Widyatmani, P., Nanda. (2022). Overview of Postpartum Visits during the COVID-19 Pandemic in the South Denpasar Health Center I Working Area in 2022.
- [10] Wulandari, Y., Yumni, F. (2019). The Relationship of Husband Support to Postpartum Blues in Pregnant Women.
- [11] Yunitasari, E. (2020). Wellness and healthy magazine. 2 (2), 303 – 307.